

Anion-exchange Separation of some Metal Ions in Aqueous Acetone-Chloroacetic Acid Media. Part-II

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ANION-exchange studies in buffered aqueous solutions of acetic acid and in acetic acid-organic solvent were carried out by Korkisch¹ and Riley². The distribution coefficients of Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cd²⁺ in aqueous acetone-chloroacetic acid media are found out. The possible metal ion separations are reported in this communication.

Experimental

The experimental details of finding the distribution coefficients and separating the binary and tertiary mixtures have been described earlier³. Separation of mixtures were carried out by feeding the metal ion mixtures (10 ml) over the resin bed. The metal ions were eluted by suitable eluents, and estimated in 10 ml effluent fractions volumetrically⁴.

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficients of the metal ions under study were found out at 0, 20, 40, 60 and 80 percentages of acetone, and in 0.5, 1, 2 and 3 M chloroacetic acid (CA).

The distribution coefficients of Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ca²⁺ are low at 0.5 and 3 M CA solutions at all percentages of acetone, indicating the tendency of these ions to form less stable anionic complexes. The distribution coefficients of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Co²⁺ at 3 M CA are greater than those at 0.5 M CA at respective acetone percentages. Due to the presence of complexant CA in the solution, ion-exchange and the complex equilibria are at work in the solution phase. A negatively charged complexing ligand may lead to stepwise formation of complexes of various types, differing in the overall charge of the species⁵. Chloroacetate ion can form several ionic species in solution with metal ions and finally gives a stable negatively charged complex ion; consequently, the increase in metal ion uptake on anion-exchanger is observed. The distribution coefficients of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Co²⁺ increase with rise in the percentage of acetone. This finding is in accordance with the fact that when the affinity of the complexes to the resin is due to ion pairing with its functional groups or invading cations, the effective dielectric constant of the resin is lower for lower dielectric solvent, resulting in high distribution coefficients, $\epsilon(\text{water})=$

78.4, $\epsilon(\text{acetone})=21.1$. The presence of a less polar solvent favours the formation of non-dissociated metal complexes^{5,6}.

There is no measurable change in K_D values of Co²⁺ in 0.5 M CA at all percentages of acetone and upto 40% in 3 M CA. Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ have maximum K_D at 80% acetone-3M CA as compared to other metal ions. Cd²⁺ shows high K_D values at all concentrations of CA and at almost all percentages of acetone. Cd²⁺ complexes are thus the most preferred complex species for Dowex-21 K.

It is observed that Co²⁺ can be separated from Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Ni²⁺. These metals are eluted by 80% acetone-3M CA, retaining Co²⁺ on the resin, which was then stripped off by distilled water. The use of distilled water for elution of Co²⁺ and ultimately for the separation of mixture, is one of the merits of these results. Cd²⁺ is strongly bound to the resin in comparison to Cu, Mn, Co, Ni, Mg, Ca, Cu and Mn. Mg and Ca were eluted by 60% acetone-0.5 M CA, and Co and Ni eluted by 80% acetone-0.5 M CA. After complete removal of co-ion in the mixture, Cd was stripped off by 5% acetone-0.1 M CA solution. From the binary mixtures Cu/Ni/Mg/Ca/Co/Mn-Zn, Cu/Ni/Mg/Ca was eluted by 80% acetone-0.5 M CA, and Co/Mn eluted by 60% acetone-0.5 M CA solution. Zn was finally removed by 20% acetone-0.5 M CA.

Fig. 1. Elution curves of Co²⁺: (○)Mg²⁺, (●)Ca²⁺, (◊)Mn²⁺, (●)Ni²⁺, and (⊙)Cu²⁺.

In tertiary mixtures, Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni was eluted by 80% acetone-3 M CA, Co by 60% acetone-3 M CA, and Zn/Cd was eluted finally by 20% acetone-0.5 M CA and 5% acetone-0.1 M CA, respectively.

Fig. 1 shows separations of Co^{2+} from Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} .

The comparison with our earlier results⁸ reveals that the distribution coefficients of Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} in CA are greater than those in acetic acid, while those of Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} are less in CA. These values suggest higher separation factor. The metal ions are thus carried with low volume of eluent and with less duration.

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Substituted Benzophenones as Possible Prodrug Forms of Benzodiazepine Anxiolytics

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A prodrug form utilises a chemical moiety of proven biological activity (parent molecule) and seeks to deliver it to the site of action, while overcoming some inherent drawbacks, such as bitterness, odour, gastric upset, poor absorption and unsuitability for administration, etc. associated with the parent compound. A prodrug¹, upon introduction to the appropriate biological system, reverts to the parent molecule by virtue of enzymatic and/or chemical liabilities. Thus, peptidoaminobenzophenones² were prepared as prodrug forms of benzodiazepines with a view to obtain a stable water

soluble product, suitable for parenteral administration. These compounds furnished 1,4-benzodiazepines at the site of action by enzymatic cleavage of terminal amide linkage, followed by chemical cyclisation. Prompted by these observations, the authors became interested in the synthesis and biological testing of 2-[N'-substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone and their higher homologues with

different types of terminal amide linkages to study the effect of enzymatic hydrolysis. Higher homologues were synthesised to observe the relative ease of the formation of seven-, eight- or nine-membered heterocyclic systems (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer 177 or 137 grating instruments. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A 60D spectrometer (60 MHz) using CDCl_3 as solvent and TMS as internal standard.

2-Amino-5-chlorobenzophenone³ and 2-methylamino-5-chlorobenzophenone⁴ were prepared by known methods.

2-[N'-Substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenones and their homologues (1-8): To a solution of substituted amino acid (0.0015 mol) in dry dioxane (15 ml) was added thionyl chloride (0.003 mol) at 0° with stirring, and left standing overnight at room temperature. 2-Amino/methylamino-5-chlorobenzophenone (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.004 mol) were added to it and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1-3 h. The reaction mixture was poured over cold water (200 ml), and the crude product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from either ethanol or benzene-petroleum ether mixture in yields ranging 50-80%. The compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and the presence ir spectral bands at 3300-3200 (amide NH), 2950 (methylene) and 1680 cm^{-1} (amide C=O).

2-[N'-Morpholinoacetylglycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone (9): A mixture of 2-[N'-chloroacetylglycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone (3; 0.001 mol), morpholine (0.0011 mol) and triethylamine (0.002 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The separated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in 60% yield. The